

Antibody Characterization Report for Profilin-1

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: Profilin-1

Gene name: *PFN1*

Uniprot: P07737

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. This report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for Profilin-1. We used an antibody characterization pipeline [2] based on knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of commercial antibodies for Profilin-1 by immunoblot (Western blot), immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. An HAP1 *PFN1* KO line is available at Horizon discovery and was used in this study. Expression of Profilin-1 protein in HAP1 is adequate as determined through public proteomics databases, namely PaxDB [3] and DepMap [4, 5].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the Profilin-1 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration (µg/µl)	Vendors recommended applications
Proteintech	11680-1-AP	44905	AB_2163182	polyclonal		rabbit	0.37	Wb,IF
Proteintech	67390-1-Ig*	10014183	AB_2924436	monoclonal	3A12E8	mouse	2.3	Wb,IF
Bio-Techne	MAB7779*	CHHC0112101	AB_2885149	monoclonal	816536	mouse	1.0	Wb
Bio-Techne	NBP2-59778*	MAB-03023	AB_2885159	monoclonal	CL3524	mouse	0.5	Wb
Bio-Techne	NBP2-67078*	HK0713	AB_2827372	monoclonal	JA30-13	rabbit	1.0	Wb, IF
GeneTex	GTX102072	40660	AB_1241179	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.56	Wb,IF
Cell Signaling Technology	3246**	1	AB_2163185	recombinant-mono	C56B8	rabbit	n/a	Wb
ABclonal	A9188**	106890101	AB_2863682	recombinant-mono	-	rabbit	2.79	Wb
Structural Genomics Consortium	AC-PFN1-4***a	YSPFN1A-c002	n/a	recombinant-mono	AC-PFN1-4	human	1.13	IP
Aviva Systems Biology	ARP48269	QC20112-42607	AB_1294625	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.5	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-25113*	VL3152362	AB_2725111	monoclonal	OT11D5	mouse	1.0	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-25120*	VL3152363	AB_2725112	monoclonal	OT12D2	mouse	0.58	Wb,IF
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-32683**	VL3152615	AB_2809960	recombinant-mono	JA30-13	rabbit	1.0	Wb,IF
Abcam	ab242369*	GR3380758-1	AB_2885122	monoclonal	CL3524	mouse	0.5	Wb
Abcam	ab133529*	GR98050-4	AB_2885087	recombinant-mono	EPR6303	rabbit	0.057	Wb
Abcam	ab124904**	GR3233753-5	AB_10975882	recombinant-mono	EPR6304	rabbit	0.143	Wb,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

^a AC-PFN1-4** sequence:

EVQLLESGGGLVQPGGSLRLSCAASGFTFYSSYMYWVRQAPGKGLEWVSSISYGGYTYADSVKGRFTISRDNKNTLYLQMNSLRAEDTAVYYCARWDGYMDYWGQGLTVTVSSGGGGSGGGGGGGG
GSDIQMTQSPSSLSASVGRVITTCRASQSISSYLNWYQQKPKAPKLLIYAASSLQSGVPSRFSGSGSDFTLTISLQPEDFATYYCQQYWDYGLPTFGQGTKLEIK

<https://www.eubopen.org/antibodies>

Table 2: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	genotype
Horizon Discovery	C631	CVCL_Y019	HAP1	WT
Horizon Discovery	HZGHC005831c016	CVCL_C4J6	HAP1	<i>PFN1</i> KO

Figure 1: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunoblot.

Lysates of HAP1 WT and *PFN1* KO were prepared, and 50 µg of protein were processed for immunoblot with the indicated Profilin-1 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. Antibody dilution used: 11680-1-AP at 1/6000, 67390-1-Ig* at 1/30000, MAB7779* at 1/5000, NBP2-59778* at 1/1000, NBP2-67078* at 1/2000, GTX102072 at 1/3000, 3246** at 1/1000, A9188 at 1/30000, AC-PFN1-4** at 1/1000, ARP48269 at 1/2000, MA5-25113* at 1/2000, MA5-25120* at 1/2000, MA5-32683** at 1/2000, ab242369* at 1/2000, ab133529* at 1/10000, ab124904** at 1/30000. Predicted band size: 15 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

HAP1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated Profilin-1 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein G or protein A or Flag-M2 magnetic beads. Samples were washed and processed for immunoblot with the indicated Profilin-1 antibody. For immunoblot, MA5-25120* was used at 1/5000. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=2% starting material; UB=2% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

HAP1 WT and *PFN1* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with glass bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated Profilin-1 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Primary antibodies were tested at 1.0 µg/ml. Bar = 10 µm.

Figure 1: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunoblot

Figure 2: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (1/3)

Figure 3: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (2/3)

Figure 3: Profilin-1 antibody screening by immunofluorescence (3/3)

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested Profilin-1 antibodies are listed in Table 1. Peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 62-6520 and 65-6120). Peroxidase-conjugated monoclonal anti-Flag M2 is from MilliporeSigma (cat. number A8592). Alexa-555-conjugated goat anti-mouse and anti-rabbit secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21424 and A21429).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in DMEM high glucose (GE Healthcare cat. number SH30081.01) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent cat. number 609065, 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent cat. number 450201).

Antibody screening by immunoblot

Immunoblots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. HAP1 WT and *PFN1* KO were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number 78429). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and immunoblot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Immunoblots were performed with precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WG1201BOX), ran with MES buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP000202), LDS sample buffer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0008) with 1x sample reducing agent (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number NP0009) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau staining which is scanned to show together with individual immunoblot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% bovine serum albumin in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106)

prior to detection with iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg or 20 µl of antibody at an unknown concentration to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively) or anti-Flag M2 magnetic beads from MilliporeSigma (cat. number M8823). Tubes were rocked for ~2 hrs at 4°C followed by several washes to remove unbound antibodies.

HAP1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates are rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~2 hrs at 4°C. Following centrifugation, the unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and immunoblot on precast midi 10% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [8]. HAP1 WT and *PFN1* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in 96 well glass plates (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary Profilin-1 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 µg/ml for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro confocal high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa568 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 x 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Background was subtracted using a minimum projection of all images collected in the Alexa568 channel. Images shown for the Alexa568 channel were modified by applying a Gaussian blur filter with a radius value of one pixel. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

References

1. Laflamme, C., et al., *Opinion: Independent third-party entities as a model for validation of commercial antibodies*. *N Biotechnol*, 2021. **65**: p. 1-8 DOI: 10.1016/j.nbt.2021.07.001.
2. Laflamme, C., et al., *Implementation of an antibody characterization procedure and application to the major ALS/FTD disease gene C9ORF72*. *Elife*, 2019. **8** DOI: 10.7554/eLife.48363.
3. Wang, M., et al., *Version 4.0 of PaxDb: Protein abundance data, integrated across model organisms, tissues, and cell-lines*. *Proteomics*, 2015. **15**(18): p. 3163-8 DOI: 10.1002/pmic.201400441.
4. Nusinow, D.P., et al., *Quantitative Proteomics of the Cancer Cell Line Encyclopedia*. *Cell*, 2020. **180**(2): p. 387-402 e16 DOI: 10.1016/j.cell.2019.12.023.
5. *DepMap, Broad*. 2019.
6. Ayoubi, R., P.S. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody Screening by Immunoblot*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717510>.
7. Ayoubi, R., et al., *Antibody screening by Immunoprecipitation*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717516>.
8. Alshafie, W., P. McPherson, and C. Laflamme, *Antibody screening by Immunofluorescence*. 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5717498>.